

Enhancing of Peaceful Co-Existence and National Integration through Religious Education

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Abstract

This paper explored the promotion of peaceful coexistence and national integration through religious education. Religion appeals to human consciences to live in peace with one another and serves as a uniting force that promotes peaceful coexistence and national unity. The data used was obtained from both primary and secondary sources such as observations, books, magazines and the internet. This paper argues that religious education inculcates moral virtues such as love, justice, honesty, kindness, and tolerance in citizens, introduces harmony and order into social activities, and achieves peaceful coexistence, national integration, and development. Therefore, where there is strife and resentment, there is neither growth nor development. The government should make religious education compulsory from kindergarten to high school so that they can acquire the correct moral virtues. Effective religious education, the promotion of moral values by religious teachers and leaders should be promoted to enable peaceful coexistence and national integration.

Keywords: Peaceful coexistence, national integration and religious education

Introduction

Peaceful coexistence is an essential factor in promoting the development and growth of societies. Peace is action that breaks down social barriers, creates harmony, and promotes social and economic stability and national unity. Okobia Faith and Osajie Justina argue that religion is a powerful factor as old as humanity. It has influenced and permeated every aspect of human life, society, economy, politics and culture.¹ Amolo argues that religion integrates all aspects of life as it tests every human experience. They further state that human interests can be viewed as religious interests. Religion brings harmony, discipline and order to social activity and gives direction and purpose. Religion influences human character as well as human ethical standards, moral behavior, and standards of judgment.² Ottuh and Onimhawo posit that all human societies are in some crises, and Nigeria is no exception. Since its independence in 1960, it has faced many crises, including ethnic, political, social and economic crises, but since no conscientious religion has been adopted, all methods of resolving these crises have failed. Religion, the social conscience and watchdog, promotes peaceful coexistence because it inculcates the correct moral values for individuals to live in peace.³

Nigeria is experiencing ethnic, political, social and economic crises because religious virtues are not inculcated into individuals which made many Nigerians to be sleeping with one eye open as a result of fear, tension and insecurity. Hence the need for religious education which inculcates the right morals into individuals and encourages love for one another and peaceful co-existence which will restore sanity to the nation and enhance national integration. The methodology used in this study was historical. Historical methods usually determine the history of past events in order to understand and interpret current events and predict the future. This method allowed researchers to trace how religious education could promote peaceful coexistence and national integration. This work covered two main areas of data collection: primary and secondary sources such as observations, books, journals and the Internet. These sources were used because of their power to provide essential information for work of this nature.

Conceptual Framework

An attempt has been made to define the keywords that make up the title of this article: peaceful coexistence, national integration and religious education.

Peace

Alawode defined peace as harmony, which is the absence of hostility. It is freedom from conflict between individuals and social groups, and freedom from the fear of violence.⁴ Ottuh and Onimhawo defined peace as the absence of social conflict that helps individuals and groups in society achieve their goals.⁵ *Oxford Dictionary* defines tranquility as a state of peace and freedom from chaos. No violence, no war, no fear, no worries⁶. *Collins English Dictionary* defined peace as a situation in which a state does not interfere in the internal affairs of another country in order to avoid war.⁷

Peaceful Coexistence

Tansi stated that peace is a state of absence of war, violence, conflict, intolerance, discrimination, or disagreement between individuals or groups in society. It is a situation in society where there is harmony, tranquility, law and order, tolerance and unity among individuals.⁸ He further argued that coexistence means living with other people of different cultures and backgrounds. To live in peaceful coexistence therefore means that different people live together in a state of peace.

Religion

Oxford Dictionary defines religion as a critical encounter with a supreme being, to whom humans respond to throughout their lives for self-realization.⁹ Okobia defined religion as the belief in supernatural beings to protect, guide and direct human affairs and the course of nature.¹⁰ Agag¹⁰ defined religion as part of a social system that gives society social and cultural identity and self-affirmation. Religion answers questions such as “Why am I here, why am I created, where am I going after here on earth.” Suleiman defines religious education as the process by which a person learns what society believes to be related to God. He further defined religious education as a process aimed at introducing new generations to the attitudes, beliefs, and practices of religious beliefs in order to provide wrong individuals with a center of unity in their lives. Religious education can be viewed as an education that develops and matures an individual's skills, attitudes and abilities.¹²

Integration

Is the act or process of combining two or more things to work together. Adebayo defines integration as the process of progressively eliminating animosity, reducing cultural and regional choices and differences, and creating a homogenous political entity.¹³ According to Usue, integration is the gathering of people from different ethnic groups into unrestricted and equal federation in the society.¹⁴ National integration is the equal right of different ethnic, religious, economic, social and political groups on national issues.¹⁵ Adebayo stated that national integration means building equitable social entities that give each inhabitant a sense of belonging, a satisfying level of participation in decision-making and development, and a transition to appropriate social resource sharing. It is a process suitable for allowable life.¹⁶ Bellode defined national integration as the harmonious coexistence of different social groups.¹⁷

National integration is the uniting of a country or the various ethnic groups of a country in such a way that they see each other as brothers and sisters, freed from tribalism, nepotism and all other vices that polarize people. According to Okobia and Osajie the integration of different ethnic and religious groups within the country should emphasize the need for national unity to exist as a starting point towards sustainable peace.¹⁸ In most pluralistic societies, promoting national integration is often a conscious national task. Policies are pursued to promote loyalty of individuals and groups to the state and its institutions in order to generate patriotic citizens from hostile groups. According to Jega, in Nigeria, national integration is a process of building unity in diversity and striving for

national unity. This means Nigerians coming together with one voice, understanding the situation in their country, and uniting to defend her sovereignty. This kind of action implies a collective responsibility to do things together in a true spirit of brotherhood.¹⁹

The Importance of Religion

Religion teaches morals and shapes character. It is the process of guiding the character and development of individuals in society so that they can do what is right and what is just. Provides the inspiration needed to fight and advance national unity. Religion pervades every aspect of human life. It emphasizes the moral consciousness that is the life wire of any society, because morally conscious individuals think better, act better, live with dignity, move away from tribalism and selfishness, and promote peaceful coexistence and national integration. Religions are essential institutions that have the power to bring about desirable change in people. Religion critiques the existing social order and is a powerful revolution for order when humans and unjust societies are moved towards social injustice, lack of the common good, embezzlement, bad interpersonal relationships, tribalism and selfishness.

It creates strength and leads to peaceful coexistence and hinders national integration. Religions share the world's consciousness as a single place, armed with transcendental points of reference, and taking their positions as guardians of truth and judges of human thought and values. Religion promotes the survival of freedom and raises social standards through constant criticism that stabilizes all societies. It supports human emancipation, social justice; good human relations, respect for human life; discipline and social transformation that help individuals become useful members of society, and promote peaceful coexistence and national integration.

The Role of Religion in Promoting Peaceful Coexistence and National Integration

It plays an important role in promoting national integration, public interest and justice. Below are some of the ways religion promotes peace and national unity.

i. Religion acts as a unifying factor

Religion acts as a means of unifying different ethnic and political groups within the country. The Nigerian government has encouraged national integration that promotes religious diversity. Ayinla noted that the Nigerian Constitution seeks to enforce unity through religious diversity. For the most part, state machinery has been used and public funds have been spent to strengthen religions that foster peaceful coexistence and integration. Examples include the observance of religious holidays such as Eid Fitr, Eid Kabir, Easter and Christmas as a unifying factor for different ethnic groups. A public oath based on the Quran and the Bible and an official government request that Muslims and Christians should pray on specific occasions. Oloso²¹ also supports religion as a unifying factor, noting that Muslim, Christian, and political leaders exchange greetings during festivals.²⁰

ii. Harmony of People's Interests

A society consists of individuals with different interests and values linked together by a network of social relationships. This social relationship must be maintained by harmonizing individual interests in what they affirm and what they deny, regardless of their interests and values, and must correspond to the values that society upholds. Ubrurhe stated that the formation and maintenance of any society depends on the existence of consensus. Religion helps create this necessary consensus by imposing sanctions on certain behaviors that may hinder the survival of society. Furthermore, individuals within society accept these sanctions or prohibitions because they believe they were provided by God or other supernatural beings. Upholding sanctions or prohibitions has appropriate consequences for supernatural beings and some members of society. Religion thus helps to control behavior and is therefore a means of social control.²²

iii. Justice

According to Bird²³, justice is the practice of one giving what is due to another by constant and continuous will. It also gives everyone what is rightfully theirs. Justice originates in all human environments, and religion

emphasizes justice and opposes all forms of injustice. It also values justice and promotes peaceful coexistence and good interpersonal relationships. Justice, therefore, is the value on which all human relationships depend and necessary for national integration. Obiefuna and Izuegbuposit that justice is a hallmark of harmonious existence and national unity, and a prerequisite for social relations and behavior.²⁴ As stated in John 8:32, religion condemns lies and injustice and defends truth and justice. Truth is life and justice is done only when it is told. It means that truth is tied to social order. Justice includes fairness, harmony, honesty and goodwill that are essential to national unity. A fair person is straightforward, truthful, honest, predictable, and fair behavior is behavior that is performed as it should be. Justice is thus understood to be the linear path upon which all human beings and all human actions conform and promote peaceful coexistence and national unity. Religion encourages people to avoid deceiving and oppressing the poor and vulnerable.

Therefore, if Nigerian leaders can absorb the principles of justice, good governance will be achieved. Many states in Nigeria today are stagnant and people are suffering, because some leaders and followers find it difficult to tell who to do what. Injustice and selfish behavior can only be stopped when good morals such as honesty and transparency permeate the lives of individuals. In most cases, Nigerians have seen many representatives representing their pockets, not the people. This leads to the negligence of the people. Therefore, Nigeria's leaders should consult the people before making and implementing decisions to improve the development of the country, as peace and unity foster progress and development. The enthronement of justice therefore helps stop various practices of injustice and inequality in the nation and promote peaceful coexistence and national integration.

iv. Good Human Relations

Religion aims to improve the interpersonal relations of citizens of our community. Interpersonal problems involve an individual's reaction to situations that lead to chaos. Most of the time, individuals are harassing themselves and others in the community. Some symptoms of interpersonal problems are emotional depression, hatred and inferiority complexes. Moreover, these interpersonal issues create attitudes that determine interpersonal relationships. Examples include manifestations of hostility and uncontrollable emotional temperament. A citizen's behavior can affect relationships with others. For this reason, religion seeks to improve the intra and interpersonal relationships of its followers through socialization institutions such as homes, schools, churches and mosques in the following ways:²⁵

- a. By helping individuals develop qualities such as patience and tolerance in discussing issues and interacting with one another in society.
- b. By making people appreciate and develop the practical qualities of good neighborly relations, sacrificial love and respect for the worth and dignity of others, and fair play.
- c. By valuing humanity and civility intra and interpersonal relationships when dealing with ourselves and others.
- d. By making citizens understand the realities of life and the need to take positive action to resolve personal and interpersonal problems.

The Importance of Peace

Motunrayo states that meaningful development cannot be achieved in an atmosphere of resentment and chaos. Societies devastated by war, conflict and civil strife are therefore more likely to experience lagging and stagnation than progress and development. It can only be achieved when people live together peacefully, regardless of their religious beliefs.²⁶ The importance of peace are as follows:

1. Peace is a fundamental part of community development, personal growth and national survival.
2. Peace promotes productivity and a meaningful life.
3. It promotes social stability and sustainability.
4. Peace enhances the quality of life.

5. Peace is the fabric of society, because the survival of individuals depends on it. Peaceful coexistence is necessary because people need each other to succeed in life.

6. Peace makes people act well, argue well, and function well.

7. Peace promotes health and longevity.

Sabater states that knowing how to live together in harmony is an essential element of human life, arising from both the mind and the spirit. This allows us to understand society better, reach consensus, solve problems more easily, and move forward together.²⁷ Peaceful coexistence is also a pillar underpinning many aspects of human life. As highly sociable creatures, living together peacefully, effectively and harmoniously ensures survival as a group and contributes to well-being and progress. Rojas posited that to ensure harmonious coexistence, we need an agreement, a word of goodwill and a peace treaty which requires human commitment and willpower.²⁸ According to Tansi, the issues related to lack of peaceful coexistence are anxiety and loss of life, stagnation and lack of progress, disorder and lack of discipline, administrative Violations, disagreements and misunderstandings, tribalism, prejudice and hatred. Therefore, we need a religious education that teaches us to live in peace with each other.²⁹

The Role of Religious Education in Promoting Peaceful Coexistence and National Integration

Sulaiman and Yemisi stated that the common principles of peace are found in all religions, no religion preaches violence and conflict, as all religions preach peace and peaceful coexistence between citizens.³⁰ The founder of Christianity, Jesus Christ, is the Prince of Peace. In Isaiah 9:6 prophet Isaiah prophesied that Jesus is the Prince of Peace. In Matthew 5:9, Jesus taught his disciples to be peace makers. Colossians 3:15 says, "Let the peace of God reign in your heart." As the peace of God reigns in the hearts of men, there will be peaceful coexistence. Jesus showed love and maintained peace with people throughout his earthly ministry.

Islam is a religion of peace, Alao stated that Islam seeks peace, tolerance and kindness which is a state of physical, mental and social harmony.³¹ Another virtue of Islam is that Muslims are required to embrace a spirit of kindness and forgiveness (Q3:124). They were also asked to live in harmony and peace with those around them. Prophet Muhammad helped the people of Mecca during the famine, even though they were banished from their homeland. Moreover, after Mecca was conquered, the people of Mecca expected him to execute them, enslave them, or confiscate their property. Instead, he called on the heathens of Mecca that no one would condemn or harm them. These are the behaviors expected of Muslims as exemplified by the prophets of Islam. Adherents should therefore promote national unity and peaceful coexistence because without peace, there will be no progress, no development and no national unity.

According to Okobia Okafor and Osajie, traditional African religion promotes peaceful coexistence because of their emphasis on communal living that coordinates the social interactions of people toward common goals. Interpersonal relationships go beyond biological affinity to share, care and depend on each other by expressing the value of togetherness. What happens to one happens to the whole community.³² This is beautifully expressed by Mbiti.³³ Igboin stated that the dignity of human life is of paramount importance as it brings respect and dignity to human beings and promotes peaceful coexistence. Respect for humanity goes beyond the nuclear family because members of an extended family, community, or tribe are viewed as brothers who must sustain and protect life. He further explained that moral values are social in nature and arise from interdependence, relationships. Peaceful coexistence leads to more knowledge of how we relate to each other, broadens one's horizons, makes individuals more useful to society, and promotes peaceful coexistence and national integration.

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Conclusion and Recommendations

Peaceful coexistence and national unity can only be achieved in Nigeria if sanctity of life, love, respect for human values and dignity, hospitality, contentment, kindness, patience and self-control taught by religions, are held by all citizens. These moral virtues will boost their morale and make Nigeria a free society where national

resources are shared fairly and where respect is accorded to all individuals regardless of tribe, ethnicity or religious beliefs. Therefore, correct moral such as honesty and transparency should be installed in citizens through religious education. Governments should promote a conscious agenda that produces patriotic citizens. Religious values should be learned and internalized by shaping the socialization process of the formative child. Religion should be integrated into national policies designed for national development. Religious teachers must consistently promote morality and ethical values and impart religious knowledge to their students. Children should be encouraged to display appropriate moral values in dealing with those around them. Religious leaders should act as good ambassadors of their religion by demonstrating moral values such as kindness, tolerance, forgiveness and good human relations. All citizens should seek peace and strive for peaceful coexistence with all people, regardless of their cultural background or religion.

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